

English Proficiency, Performance and Training Needs of Secondary English Teachers in Goa District, Camarines Sur, Philippines

Cristopher B. Narvato^{1,2,3}

¹Goa Community College, La Purisima St., Goa, Camarines Sur

²School of Graduate Studies and Research, Partido State University, Goa, Camarines Sur

³Partido State University, Goa, Camarines Sur

Abstract: - This study examined the English proficiency, training needs, and teaching performance of secondary English teachers in Goa District, Goa, Camarines Sur for the academic year 2018-2019. It assessed teachers' English proficiency, identified their training needs (particularly in language skills, teaching strategies, and instructional materials), evaluated their teaching performance, and explored the relationship between proficiency and teaching effectiveness. The study used descriptive, evaluative, and correlational methods, with data gathered through questionnaires, interviews, and documentary analysis, involving 27 teachers. Key findings included a proficiency level of "competent user" (band score 6.22), with listening skills identified as the weakest area. Teachers expressed a need for training in organizing information, teaching methods, and developing suitable reading materials. Performance ratings indicated strong subject knowledge and teaching strategies, but room for improvement in classroom management. A significant relationship between English proficiency and teaching performance was found, suggesting higher proficiency leads to better teaching outcomes. The study recommends training focused on listening, reading skills, teaching strategies, and material development. It also advocates for ongoing professional development, including graduate studies and research on communicative competence. Additionally, it supports using English proficiency tests as part of teacher hiring criteria, in line with DepEd's policies on teacher qualifications.

Keywords:- Proficiency, Training Needs, Teaching Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to speak English fluently is being recognized around the world. In the 2019 study of Education First (EF), Philippines ranked 20th in English Proficiency Index (EPI) among 100 economies (2nd among the 25 countries in Asia after Singapore). Besides the score of 60.14 or high proficiency, the country eroded its rank for 7 notches since 2016. Another study claimed that country lags behind some ASEAN neighbors in English proficiency behind Singapore and Malaysia (Warren, 2018) and that the English proficiency of college graduates in the country is lower than of the secondary level students in Thailand (Morillo, 2018). The

decline of English proficiency in the country affects its global employability (Hopkins International Partners, 2018).

However, a year after the said study Hopkins International Partners (2018) revealed the decline of English Proficiency in the country, affecting the global employability. Moreover, Wallen, (2018) claimed that the Philippines lags behind most of its ASEAN neighbors in English proficiency behind Singapore (5th) and Malaysia (13th). This was supported by (Morillo 2018) that the level of English proficiency of College graduates from the Philippines is lower than the target English proficiency of High school students in Thailand.

Parallel to this, the results of the National Achievement Test for 2016-2019 showed that there was low performance in English among high school students. It is obvious that English proficiency level of our students is declining. Most of the students have difficulties in using the language both in oral and written modes. They were found to have low mastery level in English. Many factors are found to be the reasons why the students have such performance particularly in their English subject. Ramirez (2012) claims that there are at least three. One is the exposure of students in the use of the language. Second, teachers of other subjects who are supposed to use English as medium of instruction are using the first language. Third, some of the teachers handling English subject have also an average English proficiency level. Teachers play an important role in the educative process. They are considered the agents of change in the educational system. Teachers' main goal is to make students learn effectively and efficiently. In order to achieve this goal, they must have the full mastery of the subject matter and must possess necessary skills and trainings relative to the subject matter they teach. It is also an advantage if they have the command of the English language as a *lingua franca*.

Teachers' English proficiency has been recognized as an important qualification for successful English teaching (Butler, 2004; Lee; 2004; Nunan, 2003). For example, Nunan (2003, p.601) stated, "... a major problem is that many English teachers simply do not have the proficiency". It would be possible that a teacher with high –enough language proficiency may feel confident in teaching English, while having low level of proficiency, teachers may feel less confident in teaching school or college students.

Furthermore, Crisostomo, (2013), pointed out that English teachers in public schools who are not fluent in the language will only produce poor quality students thus, they need to undergo a re-training program to be qualified to teach the subject. High achieving schools (in English Proficiency) have teachers with sound knowledge of their subject matter, sound pedagogical knowledge and skill, and good classroom management skill De Jesus, (2011).

Teachers' competency' as defined by Spencer & Spencer (1993), refers to a professional knowledge, professional skill and professional value which are possessed by the teacher himself/herself and are related to implement the successful teaching.

Hence, there is a need to investigate the English proficiency level of the English secondary teachers in Goa, Camarines Sur and assess their trainings to improve their English teaching capability and the English proficiency of the students.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study used the descriptive – evaluative and correlational method of research. This study was an endeavor to investigate the following; 1.) English Proficiency Level of Secondary English Teachers in Goa District; 2.) Training needs of Secondary English Teachers along: a. Identifying concepts, b. teaching strategies, c. instructional materials/aids; 3.) Level of teaching performance of English Teachers as rated by: a. students, b. peers. c. school heads; 4.) Significant relationship between the English Proficiency level and the teaching performance of the secondary English teachers. The test of hypothesis would like to prove if there is a significant relationship between the proficiency level and the teaching performance of the secondary English teachers.

This study involved four major phases namely: Phase 1- Preparation phase, 2- Data gathering stage, 3- Analysis and interpretation of data and 4- Writing of the manuscript. In the Phase 1, it included the preparation phase where the researcher gathered necessary data related to the study. After which, the researcher asked permission from the concerned officials before the final start of the study. The researcher made questionnaire was constructed based on the stated problems of the study which was subjected for validation by three language experts. Suggestions, recommendations were taken for the improvement of the research questionnaire. Pilot-testing of the research instruments was followed in order to test the reliability and validity.

Phase 2 included the data gathering phase. A validated questionnaire-checklist was used as the main data gathering instrument of the study; a follow-up interview was used primarily to clarify vague answers; and documentary analysis was employed to answer the specific question concerning the status of English teacher's performance in the teaching-learning situation. It was administered at teachers who were excluded in the study. Respondents of this study were thirty (27) English teachers from Goa District.

Phase 3 was the analysis and interpretation of the raw data. The data gathered through the use of documentary analysis, questionnaire – checklist and informal interviews was sorted, tabulated and analyzed by making use of appropriate statistical treatment. Finally, Phase 4 included the writing of the final paper incorporating all the suggestions and comments of the panel of evaluators. This included the formulation of intervention program which may address the weaknesses of teacher in terms of proficiency. Any probable outcome of this investigation especially on the English Proficiency Level measured, and the performance of Secondary English Teachers that may crop up can provide insights to the researcher to propose a functional intervention program. The respondents of the study involved all (27) public secondary school English teachers of Goa District. No sampling technique was used since the universal population of respondents was utilized. The needed information was obtained through the use of documentary analysis, questionnaire – checklist and unstructured interview.

To give meaning to the data gathered, the study used Pearson – Product- Moment Coefficient of Correlation. This parametric test was used to answer problem regarding the extent of relationship between English proficiency level and the teaching performance of the Secondary English teachers. The recommendations and suggestions were integrated to the revision of the content of the supplementary reading comprehension material using local content.

III. RESULTS

➤ *English Proficiency Level of Secondary English Teachers of Goa District*

Table 1 shows the detailed presentation of Secondary English Teachers ' English Proficiency level along listening, reading and writing skills.

The foregoing table reveals that most of the respondents are modest in listening skill with a computed band score ranging from 5.0 to 5.5 as indicated by the frequency count of 11 or 73.33%. This could mean that the concerned teachers has partial command of the language, coping with overall meaning in most situations though is likely to make many mistakes, should be able to handle basic communication in own field.

Along the aspect of reading skill, it can also be observed that most of the teachers are competent users as revealed by the computed band score ranging from 5.51 to 6.5 as indicated by the frequency count of 13 or 86.66%. The adjectival rating of competent user tries to show that the Instructor – respondents has generally effective command of the language despite some inaccuracies, inappropriacies and misunderstandings. With this particular rating, they can use and understand fairly complex language, particularly in familiar situations.

The assessment of teachers writing skills reveal much better performance and they tend to be good users as writers as revealed by the computed band score ranging from 6.51 to 7.5 and as indicated by the frequency count of 11 or 73.33%.

As good users in writing, they have operational command of the language, though with occasional inaccuracies, inappropriateness and misunderstandings in some situations.

But, generally they can handle complex language well and understand detailed reasoning.

Table 1 English Proficiency Level of Teachers Along Listening, Reading and Writing Skills

Adjectival Rating	Band Score Bracket	LISTENING		READING		WRITING	
		f	percent	F	percent	f	percent
Modest user	5.0 -5.5	11	73.33	1	6.66	0	0.0
Competent User	5.51- 6.5	4	26.66	13	86.66	3	20
Good User	6.51-7.5	0	0.0	1	6.66	11	73.33
Very Good User	7.51 -8.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	6.66

The overall English Proficiency level of teachers as revealed in table 2 indicates that the respondents are competent users. This represent the modal class of the distribution since most of the respondents around 10 or

66.66%. As competent users, they should not be contented by what they are, they need to aim more a little bit higher say as very good or expert users.

Table 2 Presents the Summary Table for Overall English Proficiency Level of Teachers.

Overall English Proficiency Level of Secondary English Teachers

Adjectival Rating	Band Score Bracket	Number	Percent	Modal Class
Competent User	5.51-6.5	10	66.66	Competent User
Good User	6.51-7.5	5	33.33	

➤ *Training Needs of Teachers*

Training Needs of Teachers in Terms of Identifying Concepts

The data revealed that in terms of Identifying concept, teachers need training in categorizing information with implicit relationship (Mw=3.58); Classifying information with a focus (Mw=3.53) and explaining (interpreting) information by separating relevant from irrelevant information (Mw=3.42) while training on assimilating new

information with old information based on principle or cause –effect relationship (Mw=3.13) is moderately needed by teachers.

This indicates that teachers lack training in categorizing, classifying and explaining information with implicit relationship of relevant from irrelevant information. This means that teachers found these indicators most useful in the classroom.

Table 3 Training Needs of Teachers in Terms of Identifying Concepts

Indicators	School No.						GMw	Verbal Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Classifying information with a focus	3.66	3.75	4.66	3.0	3.1	3.0	3.53	Very much needed
Grouping information with a focus	3.5	3.75	4.33	3.0	3.4	2.5	3.41	Very much needed
Categorizing information with implicit relationship	3.5	3.75	4.33	3.0	3.4	3.5	3.58	Very much needed
Categorizing information with explicit relationship	3.5	3.5	3.0	3.0	3.4	3.5	3.32	Moderately needed
Comparing information with a focus	3.5	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.4	3.5	3.23	Moderately needed
Comparing information with a focus	3.66	3.0	4.33	3.0	3.2	2.5	3.28	Moderately needed
Explaining (interpreting) information by logical relationships	3.33	3.75	3.0	3.6	3.4	2.5	3.26	Moderately needed
Explaining (interpreting) information by separating relevant from irrelevant information	3.5	3.5	3.0	3.6	3.4	3.5	3.42	Very much needed
Organizing information based on principles or cause –effect relationships	3.66	3.75	3.0	2.6	3.4	3.5	3.32	Moderately needed
Assimilating new information with old information based on principle or cause –effect relationships	3.5	3.0	3.0	2.6	3.2	3.5	3.13	Moderately needed
Applying principles or cause – effect relationships to explain new information	3.5	3.75	3.0	3.0	3.4	2.5	3.19	Moderately needed
Applying principles or cause – effect relationships to predict trends or events	3.5	3.75	3.0	3.0	3.4	2.5	3.19	Moderately needed

Legend: Extremely Need-4.20-5.00; Very Much Needed-3.40-4.19; Moderately Needed-2.60-3.39; Slightly Needed 1.80-2.59; Not Needed -1.00-1.79

➤ *Training Needs of Teachers in Terms of Strategies/Methods*

The data revealed that in terms of training needs in teaching strategies/methods, the teachers very much needed trainings on appropriate use of practice and drill and variety

of challenging practice and drill (Mw=3.97) and teaching methods for independent practice- 3.8 while asking low-level and high-level questions got the lowest weighted mean of 3.19.

Table 4 Training Needs of Teachers in Terms of Strategies/Methods

Indicators	School No.						GMw	Verbal Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Appropriate use of practice and drill	3.66	4.5	4.66	3.4	4.6	3.0	3.97	<i>Very much needed</i>
Providing corrective feedback	3.51	3.5	4.33	3.4	3.4	3.0	3.52	<i>Very much needed</i>
Providing students with methods for independent practice	3.66	4.0	4.33	4.0	3.8	3.0	3.8	<i>Very much needed</i>
Monitoring seatwork	3.66	4.5	4.33	3.4	3.8	2.5	3.7	<i>Very much needed</i>
Conduct of remedial teaching	4.0	3.5	4.33	4.0	3.8	3.0	3.77	<i>Very much needed</i>
Provides variety and challenging practice and drill	3.66	4.5	4.66	3.4	4.6	3.0	3.97	<i>Very much needed</i>
Keeping students alert and focused on the task	3.83	3.5	3.66	3.2	4.0	4.0	3.7	<i>Very much needed</i>
Skills in striking a balance between factual and thought-provoking questions.	3.66	3.5	3.0	2.6	3.8	3.0	3.26	<i>Very much needed</i>
Asking low-level and high-level questions	3.66	3.5	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.19	<i>Very much needed</i>
Asking convergent and divergent questions	3.66	3.5	4.66	2.6	4.2	3.0	3.6	<i>Very much needed</i>
Asking questions related to the cognitive taxonomy	3.66	3.25	4.66	3.0	4.0	3.5	3.68	<i>Very much needed</i>
Making use of comments and praise to the right person at the right time	3.0	3.5	4.66	2.6	4.2	3.0	3.49	<i>Very much needed</i>
The art of lecturing and explaining	2.6	3.35	3.66	3.2	4.4	3.0	3.37	<i>Very much needed</i>
Establishing rapport with students	3.0	3.25	4.66	3.2	4.2	3.0	3.55	<i>Very much needed</i>
Combining instructional materials	3.0	4.0	4.0	3.2	4.2	3.0	3.57	<i>Very much needed</i>
Proper use of reflective thinking	3.0	4.0	3.0	3.2	4.2	4.0	3.57	<i>Very much needed</i>

Legend: Extremely Need-4.20-5.00; Very Much Needed-3.40-4.19; Moderately Needed-2.60-3.39; Slightly Needed 1.80-2.59; Not Needed -1.00-1.79

➤ *Training Needs of Teachers in Terms of Instructional Materials/Aids*

Table 5 revealed that teachers extremely need training in selecting materials suitable to the reading level of the students (Mw=4.25); checking students reactions on instructional aid and can also consider one’s own reaction

(Mw=4.12) and using materials that can illustrate and increase the emotional impact of abstract concepts Mw=4.03) while training on relating instructional materials to the age, maturity, ability and interest of students (Mw=3.44) got the lowest weighted mean interpreted as very much needed.

Table 5 Training Needs of Teachers in Terms of Instructional Materials/Aids

Indicators	School No.						GMw	Verbal Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Appropriate use of instructional materials to enhance learning	3.83	4.0	4.66	3.2	4.0	4.0	3.95	Very much needed
Using variety of materials, media and resources to develop and maintain student interest	4.16	4.0	4.66	2.6	3.8	3.0	3.7	Very much needed
Relating instructional materials to the age, maturity, ability and interest of students	3.0	4.0	4.66	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.44	Very much needed
Focusing on students' attention on specific things to attend while viewing, listening or reading the materials	3.66	4.0	4.0	2.6	4.2	3.0	3.58	Very much needed
Relating the experience provided by the aid to the learners personal needs or goals	3.0	4.0	4.66	3.0	4.0	3.5	3.69	Very much needed
Using materials that can illustrate and increase the emotional impact of abstract concepts	3.5	4.0	4.66	2.6	4.4	5.0	4.03	Very much needed
Providing varied learning experiences through the use of materials such as workbook or paperback novel	3.5	4.0	4.0	3.2	4.4	5.0	4.02	Very much needed
Checking students reactions on instructional aid and can also consider one's own reaction	3.66	4.0	4.66	3.2	4.2	5.0	4.12	Very much needed
Selecting appropriate materials that can fit to the objectives	3.66	4.0	4.0	3.2	4.2	4.5	3.93	Very much needed
Presenting materials in technically appropriate manner	3.5	4.0	4.66	2.6	4.4	4.5	3.94	Very much needed
Selecting materials suitable to the reading level of the students	3.66	4.0	4.66	3.8	4.4	5.0	4.25	Extremely needed
Matching the difficulties of the materials to the abilities of the students	3.66	4.0	4.0	3.4	4.6	5.0	4.11	Very much needed

Legend: Extremely Need-4.20-5.00; Very Much Needed-3.40-4.19; Moderately Needed-2.60-3.39; Slightly Needed 1.80-2.59; Not Needed -1.00-1.79

➤ *Level of Teaching Performance of English Teachers*

Table 6 Level of Teaching Performance of English Teachers

Indicators	School No.						GMw	Verbal Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Knowledge of Subject Matter								
Demonstrates mastery	4.3	4.7	4.3	3.9	4.6	4.4	4.37	Outstanding
Draws and shares information	4.3	4.5	3.8	4.6	4.3	4.6	4.35	Outstanding
Integrates subject to practical circumstances and learning intents/purpose of students.	4.1	4.6	4.1	3.9	4.5	4.3	4.25	Outstanding
Explains the relevance of present.	4.3	4.6	3.7	4.4	4.5	4.5	4.33	Outstanding
Demonstrate up-to-date knowledge and/or awareness on current trends and issues of the subject.	3.9	4.6	4.1	4	4.4	4.6	4.27	Outstanding
Teaching Strategies								
Creates teaching strategies that allow students to practice using concepts they need to understand (interactive discussion)	4.4	5	4.4	4.6	4.4	4.6	4.57	Outstanding
Enhances students' self-esteem and/or gives due recognition to students.	4.1	4.8	4.2	4.1	4.3	4.6	4.35	Outstanding
Allow students to create their own course with objectives and realistically defined student-professor rules and makes them accountable for their performance.	4.1	4.6	4.2	4.4	4.1	4.5	4.32	Outstanding

Allow students to think independently and make their own decisions and holding them accountable for their performance based largely on their success in executing decisions.	4.3	4.7	4	4.1	4.5	4.4	4.33	Outstanding
Encourage students to learn beyond what is required and provides activities that develop analytical thinking.	3.8	4.8	4.1	3.9	4.8	4.6	4.33	Outstanding
Classroom Management of Learning								
Creates opportunities for intensive and/or extensive contribution of students in the class activities (e.g. breaks class into dyads, or buzz/task group).	4.3	4.7	3.9	4.3	4	4.5	4.28	Outstanding
Assumes roles as facilitator, resource person, coach, inquisitor, referee in drawing students to contribute to knowledge and understanding of the concepts at hands.	4.4	4.9	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.6	4.42	Outstanding
Designs and implements learning conditions and experience that promotes healthy exchange and/or confrontations.	4.2	4.7	4.1	4.5	4.1	4.4	4.33	Outstanding
Structures/re-structure learning and teaching-learning context to enhance attainment of collective learning objectives.	4.2	4.7	3.9	3.9	3.9	4.3	4.15	Very Satisfactory
Uses of instructional Materials to reinforce learning process.	3.3	4.7	3.9	3.6	4.2	3.5	3.87	Satisfactory
General Weighted mean	4.13	4.71	4.05	4.16	4.33	4.43	4.3	Outstanding

Legend: Outstanding (the performance almost always exceeds the job requirement. the faculty is an exceptional role model)-4.20-5.00; Very satisfactory (the performance meets and almost exceeds the job requirement)-3.40-4.19; Satisfactory (the performance meets job requirement)-2.60-3.39; Fair (the performance needs some development to meet the job requirement)-needed 1.80-2.59; Poor (The faculty fails to meet the job requirement- 1.00-1.79).

The data revealed that teachers demonstrates mastery of the subject matter (GMw=4.37) interpreted as outstanding. In terms of teaching strategies, creates teaching strategies that allow students to practice using concepts they need to understand trough interactive discussion (Mw=4.57) and classroom management of learning that enhances students' self-esteem and/or gives due recognition to students (Mw=4.35) while the use of instructional materials like audio/video materilas, field strips, films showing, computer aided instruction and other materials to reincorce learning process got the lowest weighted mean of 3.87 interpreted as satisfactory.

This implies that teachers demonstarte mastery of the subject matter and able to create strategies that provide interactive discussion however needs to provide variety of teaching materials to aid learning. It means that adequate and accessible facilites like computers and hands on activities that give authentic activities to students like field trips may be conducted to reinforce student learning.

➤ *Significant Relationship Between the English Proficiency Level and Teaching Performance*

The data indicates that there is a significant relationship at the 0.01 level of significance between the English language proficiency and teaching performance of teachers in public elementary schools in Goa District. It means that if the

language proficiency of the teachers is good, their teaching performance is also good.

Table 7 Significant Relationship between the English Proficiency Level and Teaching Performance

		VAR00001	VAR00002
VAR00001	Pearson Correlation	1	.654**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.006
	N	16	16
VAR00002	Pearson Correlation	.654**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	
	N	16	16
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

IV. DISCUSSION

The overall English Proficiency level of Secondary Teachers as revealed in table 2 indicates that the Instructor – respondents are competent users. This represent the modal class of the distribution since most of the respondents around 10 or 66.66%The data revealed that in terms of Listening, teachers are fully proficient in all indicators given. They are fully proficient in the accuracy of answers (GMw=4.70). School 6 got the highest weighted mean of 4.80 while school 2 got the lowest weighted mean of 4.31 interpreted as fully proficient.

In terms of reading, teachers are fully proficient in making inferences (GMW=4.67) interpreted as fully proficient while predicting outcomes got the lowest weighted mean of 4.0. School 3 got the highest weighted mean of 4.73 while School 6 got the lowest weighted mean of 4.20. In terms of writing, teachers are fully proficient in language use (GMw=4.66). School 4 exceeds the other schools with a weighted mean of 4.84 while School 1 got the lowest weighted mean of 4.14.

In terms of speaking, all schools showed full proficiency in diction (Mw=4.44) however showed adequate proficiency in fluency and pronunciation (Mw=3.83). School four got the highest weighted mean of 4.50 while school 6 got the lowest weighted mean of 3.66. Teachers have varying level of proficiency in listening, reading, writing and speaking. Teachers in general demonstrated full proficiency however showed adequate proficiency in speaking- fluency and pronunciation. Teachers may be sent to trainings in speaking proficiency to attain higher level of performance in teaching oral communication in the classroom. In-service training for language teachers may be given each year to address proficiency issues and concerns.

The data revealed that in terms of Identifying concept, teachers need training in categorizing information with implicit relationship (Mw=3.58); Classifying information with a focus (Mw=3.53) and explaining (interpreting) information by separating relevant from irrelevant information (Mw=3.42) while training on assimilating new information with old information based on principle or cause-effect relationship (Mw=3.13) is moderately needed by teachers. The data revealed that in terms of training needs in teaching strategies/methods, the teachers very much needed trainings on appropriate use of practice and drill and variety of challenging practice and drill (Mw=3.97) and teaching methods for independent practice- 3.8 while asking low-level and high-level questions got the lowest weighted mean of 3.19.

Table 4 revealed that teachers extremely need training in selecting materials suitable to the reading level of the students (Mw=4.25); checking students reactions on instructional aid and can also consider one's own reaction (Mw=4.12) and using materials that can illustrate and increase the emotional impact of abstract concepts Mw=4.03) while training on relating instructional materials to the age, maturity, ability and interest of students (Mw=3.44) got the lowest weighted mean interpreted as very much needed

Teachers lack training in categorizing, classifying and explaining information with implicit relationship of relevant from irrelevant information. They also need training in teaching methods with emphasis on appropriate teaching practice and drills in teaching that are suitable to the challenges and demands of the language learners. They also need training in developing reading materials suitable to the abilities of students. Teachers may undergo training on literacy analysis in order to evaluate accurately the deeper meaning and emotions the students want to portray in order

to give objective evaluation of student performance when interpreting/reacting to an article or stories read.

The data revealed that teachers demonstrates mastery of the subject matter (GMw=4.37) interpreted as outstanding. In terms of teaching strategies, creates teaching strategies that allow students to practice using concepts they need to understand through interactive discussion (Mw=4.57) and classroom management of learning that enhances students' self-esteem and/or gives due recognition to students (Mw=4.35) while the use of instructional materials like audio/video materials, field strips, films showing, computer aided instruction and other materials to reinforce learning process got the lowest weighted mean of 3.87 interpreted as satisfactory.

Teachers demonstrate mastery of the subject matter and able to create strategies that provide interactive discussion however needs to provide variety of teaching materials to aid learning. Teachers may provide hands on activities that give authentic activities to students like field trips may be conducted to reinforce student learning. The administration may provide adequate and accessible facilities like computers and speech laboratories.

The data indicate that there is a significant relationship at the 0.01 level of significance between the English language proficiency and teaching performance of teachers in public elementary schools in Goa District. The language proficiency of the teachers is related to their teaching performance. Based from the foregoing conclusions, it is recommended that the English proficiency among language teachers may be regularly enhanced. Teachers may attend seminars and trainings with emphasis on language proficiency. Teachers may also enroll to graduate studies and advance studies in linguistics.

Considering the significant relationship between language proficiency and teaching performance, the hiring committee may continuously utilize English proficiency test as one of the requirements in entering the teaching position. Although, there are other factors that affect teaching performance, English proficiency test may be regularly conducted to determine teaching effectiveness for teachers teaching English and other relevant subjects.

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